

DETERMINATION OF RADIATION LEAKAGE OF A TYPICAL COBALT-60 TELETHERAPY UNIT

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KEYWORDS: Radiation, Dosimetry, Gantry, Dose rate and Radiotherapy**ABSTRACT**

Radiation dose survey was carried out around the head of Cobalt-60 machine in ABUTH Zaria, purposely to assess the shielding integrity of the gantry. LiF TLD chips and portable digital dose rate meter (Atomtex) were used in this research. The results indicated a higher value of 1.8mSv/h and a lower 1.55mSv/h (with TLD placed on the gantry). Using Atomtex digital dose rate meter, a higher dose rate 52.00 μ Sv/h and a lower 00.62 μ Sv/h were recorded. Radiation doses ranging from 0.33 μ Sv/h to 0.65 μ Sv/h were obtained within the treatment room. The results show that the depleted lead covering the housing of the 229.061 TBq Co-60 gamma ray beam unit was able to shield the radiation source as required. The radiation dose measured was lower than the acceptable values as recommended by the ICRP.

INTRODUCTION

Radiation is a form of energy which is capable of producing biological effects on living cells (Greening, 1985). Radiation exposure occurs naturally example from cosmic rays the food we eat excreta and as a result of scientific or technological manipulations. When radiation is used at controlled level, a tremendous benefit can be derived. There is wide range of beneficial application radiation in life. Radiation and nuclear application in health science can be diagnostic, therapeutic and preventive (Groth, 2000). Radiation therapy is the last option for the treatment of cancerous cells (MLA, 2009). Amongst the types of Radiotherapy are Teletherapy, Brachetherapy and Chemotherapy.

Radiotherapy involves the treatment of cancer aimed to deliver a high radiation dose from some distance to the affected part of the patient (Alan et al 1986). The process is carried out without causing excessive injury to the surrounding healthy tissues.

Radiotherapy could be carried out with accelerated particles and x-rays or gamma rays. The gamma ray beam unit consists of Radium-226, Caesium-137 or Cobalt-60. Early units using Radium had the advantage of a long half-life and an effectively constant output dose rate. However the potential leakage of Radon gas, low specific activities and the very high photon energy made the protection of the source house of Radium very difficult. Nowadays Radium sources are replaced with Cobalt-60 sources. At "beam off" condition, the lead protects the radiographer to attend to the patients and other staff (cleaners for instance) to carry out their duties. Also at "beam off" condition, the lead reduces the level of radiation reaching parts of the patient other than the treatment area and reduces also the level of radiation reaching the walls of the treatment room. The gamma ray therefore needs to be housed in protective shield such that the gamma ray air, KERMA rates (kinetic energy absorbed per unit mass) at the surface and at 1.0m from the source are below accepted limits. The major part of the source housing will be heavy alloy, depleted Uranium or lead. This protective material will surround the sources in all direction except the direction of the useful beam. It is imperative to carry out routine leakage radiation test in any installation to ensure effective protection surrounding the head. Complete check is required to ensure leakage radiation is below the acceptable limits and to ensure there are no weaknesses such as cracks, or pinholes in the material used (Groth 2000). The concern for the paper is at the beam-off condition. In this situation any abnormal radiation can cause radiation hazard to the patients and or radiation workers. This paper presented the results of leakage radiation assessment through the limited attenuation afforded by the Cobalt-60 source housing.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

MATERIALS

The cobalt 60 was at ABUTH purposely to deliver successive doses of radiation energy to the affected part of the patient (Radiotherapy of cancer). The machine was brought to be used in Nigeria (Elegba1995) in collaboration with IAEA.

An X-ray and gamma ray digital dose rate meter (Atomtex) was the direct survey reading dosimeter used to carry out part of measurement. The other parts measurement was carried out with LiF TLD (Lithium Fluoride Thermo luminescence dosimeter) chips. The measurements were carried out at “beam off” condition. The Atomtex is self calibrated and manufactured with range 50nSv-10Sv/h. The Cobalt-60 machine was a 229.061 TBq (6190.84Ci). The CIRUS CO model was ensured leakage free at the time of manufacture. It was installed in the Oncology and Radiotherapy center at Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital in Zaria Kaduna state of Nigeria (ABUTH) The Solaro TLD reader, TLD chips and the Atom text dose rate meter were obtained CERT ABU Zaria and the measurements were carried out at the centre under professional supervision.

Figure 1.0 Head of Cobalt-60 machine (Gantry) Showing the marked survey points.

Both measurements were carried out on these points.

Following the Co-60 machine installation, the decay scheme of the radioactive isotopes is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2.0 Schematic Decay of Cobalt-60

METHODS

Two TLD chips inside envelopes separated 1.0cm were placed on the marked points. These chips were kept for a duration of 65 hours which was the estimated time at ‘beam off’ condition over the weekend. The TLD chips were pre-annealed and with the same Cobalt-60 machine at SSD (source –skin- distance) 1.0cm, the chips were then calibrated. The calibrations and all readings were effected using Solaro TLD reader.

TLD calibration: Two annealed TLDS were assigned in an envelope 1.0cm apart and each set were exposed to gamma ray radiation of the Co-60 at the same source to TLD distance but with varying time of exposure. The corresponding Doses were obtained applying.

$$\text{Dose} = \text{Dose rate} \times \text{time} \tag{1}$$

$$\text{Dose rate} = \Gamma \frac{A}{r^2} \tag{2}$$

Where $\Gamma = 0.302 \frac{\text{MGy/hr}}{\text{GBq/hr}}$ is the specific gamma activity; A is the activity of the source and r is the distance from the source to the irradiated material.

$$\text{But } A = A_0 e^{-\lambda t} \tag{3}$$

Where $\lambda = 0.693/T_{1/2}$ the radioactivity decay constant.

Co-60 has $T_{1/2} = 5.3$ years. The activity of the source was determined at the time the research using the manufacture value and applying equation 3. From equation 2 the dose rate was calculated as 885.9117mGy/min. Time of exposures were varied obtaining various doses in mGy. The corresponding number of counts were obtained and plotted

A linear relationship was established by Dose against number of counts from the TLD reader. The result was used to determine the TLD dose rate as indicated in table 1.

Within the treatment room however, the TLD chips were not used because of the limited time at beam off. The direct survey meter was used at sample points which were marked randomly. At each point, three readings were recorded and the average recorded as one value corresponding to its code. These sections will comparatively indicate whether the walls are radioactive.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the result of radiation dose measured at the gantry of the Cobalt -60 machine in the treatment room.

Table 1.0 Radiation level at the Gantry

Table 1.0 Radiation Dose level at the Gantry

Code	Dose rate (Atomtex) μSv/h at 5-10 cm	Dose rate (TLD) mSv/h on the surface
C01	52.00	1.81
C02	42.00	1.63
C03	00.62	1.55
C04	12.30	1.59
C05	29.00	1.60

Radiation dose level in the treatment room with Atomtex is carefully displayed in table 2.

Table 2.0 Radiation Dose level around the CO-60 machine

Code	Dose rate (Atomtex) $\mu\text{Sv/h}$	Description of sample points
C06	0.51	At the first wall
C07	0.65	Far, top of machine
C08	0.64	At the bench
C09	0.33	At the second wall
C010	0.55	At the third wall
C011	0.33	At the forth wall
C012	0.49	Smoke detector

DISCUSSION

(Bonford et al 2000) published in his book the leakage air, *kerma* rate permitted from gamma ray beam units at beam off 0.1 mGy/hr maximum and average 0.02mGy/hr (at 1.0m from source). At 5.0cm from the source should not exceed 2.0mGy/hr. Table 3.0

Table3.0 Leakage air kerma rates permitted from gamma ray beam units

	At 1m from Maximum	Source Average	At 5cm from surface
Beam off	0.1mGyh ⁻¹	0.02mGyh ⁻¹	2.0mGyh ⁻¹
Beam on	0.1%	–	–
Beam on (small units)	10mGyh ⁻¹	–	–

The percentage value at ‘beam on’ is of the useful beam kerma rate at 1m (Bonford et al 2000)

The dose rate obtained with the TLD is higher because it is closer to the radiation source. The TLDs were in contact with the gantry while the dose rate meter was at 5.0-10.0cm away from the gantry. Also the inconsistent of the TLD results with the dose rate meter may not be due to the fact that there is difference in the elemental material volume. since their relative distances from the gantry were not the same. Following fact that radiation dose decreases with increasing distance (inverse square law) the two results were are relatively comparable.

The TLD materials cannot be pre-annealed completely and transporting the TLD from the Teaching hospital may slightly affect the dose rate. However both measurements were carried out within fairly the same background.

Faria, (1995) published that TLDs have been extensible employed for environmental radiation measurements in some Brazilian radioactive facilities. They have low fading, high sensitivity and cumulatively. LiF is $Z_{\text{effective}}$ nearly tissue equivalent (Z_{eff} for tissue is 7.4) Christiansen et al, (1982) and Cember, (1986). Hence the TLDs used in the research are suitable.

8TH – 9TH, OCTOBER, 2013

A typical cobalt-60 teletherapy unit could be the moving source or the fixed source type. The point Co₁ has relatively limited attenuation or is at the position where the source is stationed at beam off. This maybe the account for the higher radiation recorded. The sample point Co₃ with lower radiation level, could possess higher attenuation ability or away from the radiation source (Table 1.0)

In table 2.0 however points Co₉ and Co₁₁ are farther away from the machine this may be the account of lower radiation level. These doses also indicated the presence radioactive facility. Co₈ is closer the machine and Co₇ the bench maybe induced with radiation due to strays of radiation and ionization of the surrounding.

CONCLUSION

An average radiation dose of 0.50 μ Sv/h was determined in the treatment room also showing the presence radioactive facilities. This value is slightly above the out door radiation background limit

The position co₁ is likely adjacent to the point where radiation source is positioned at beam off. The other position co₃ is farther away from the radiation source at the beam off condition or subjected to thicker lead shielding. Co₉ and Co₁₁ were indoors radiation. Although the energy of the source reduces as it decays with time prolong staying in the treatment room may cause accumulation of radiation does. Touching the gantry for long time especially at co₁ could also result to unexpected exposure which could lead to biological effect. The concern for the paper is the beam off condition .However the limited attenuation afforded by the cobalt -60 machine housing is able to shield normally the radiation source.

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